

gave the value of $\log K^{\mu=0}$. Ligational standard free energy was obtained from

$$\Delta F^0 = -RT \ln_2 K^{\mu=0}$$

Fig. 4

The thermodynamic formation constants are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC VALUES OF STABILITY CONSTANTS OF RA CHELATES (27°C)

Cation	Log K ₁	Log K ₂	Log β ₂
Cu(II)	15.60	3.95	19.55
Ni(II)	8.45	4.85	13.30
Co(II)	7.40	4.45	11.85
Mn(II)	8.20	3.40	11.60
Zn(II)	8.80	5.00	13.80
Cd(II)	9.60	4.60	14.20
Ca(II)	7.40	—	—
Mg(II)	7.60	—	—
VO(II)	8.00	7.20	15.20
UO ₂ (II)	10.40	7.20	17.60
Al(III)	10.00	5.25	15.25

From the values of formation constants, the relative tendencies of the metal ions studied for complex formation with RA are observed as follows:

From the sequence, it is observed that Irving-William's¹¹ natural order is followed in so far as $\text{Zn} < \text{Cu} > \text{Ni} > \text{Mn}$ is concerned. It is seen that the stability of Co(II) is greater than Ni(II). This may

be due to the Jahn-Teller stabilisation of Co(II). This anomaly has also been observed by a number of workers¹²⁻¹⁵.

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Potentiometric Study of Some Schiff-Base Ligands

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SCHIFF bases derived from the reaction of aromatic aldehydes with aliphatic or aromatic amines represent an important series of widely studied ligands¹⁻⁴. The present study reports the proton ligand stability constants for a series of five Schiff-base ligands obtained by the condensation of salicylaldehyde with the amines such as 2-aminopyridine, aniline, anthranilic acid, *o*-aminophenol, and *m*-aminophenol.

Experimental

All chemicals and reagents used in the study were either of A. R. Grade or purified before use.

Preparation of the Ligands :

The Schiff bases were prepared by taking stoichiometric amounts of the aldehyde and the respective amine in absolute alcohol. The mixture was heated under reflux on a water bath for 30-45 minutes when shining coloured crystals appeared. These were separated out, repeatedly recrystallised in alcohol and preserved in a vacuum desiccator. The purity of the ligands was checked by elemental analysis and determination of m. p./decomposition temp.

Lime distilled absolute alcohol and carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution were prepared⁵. Perchloric acid (0.153M) and sodium perchlorate solution were prepared in double distilled water. Perchloric acid was standardised with standard sodium hydroxide solution. Sodium perchlorate solution was standardised after passing it through a column of cation exchange resin. An Elico-pH meter model LI-10 (accuracy ± 0.05 unit) with Beckmann glass saturated calomel electrode assembly was used for the study.

Bjerrum-Calvin^{6,7} pH-titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁸ was followed to determine the "practical" proton-ligand stability constants of the ligands in 50%(V/V) water alcohol medium, kept at a constant temperature of 30° and in presence of requisite amount of sodium perchlorate to maintain constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.1M$).

Results and Discussion

The \bar{n}_A (average number of protons associated) values were calculated using the equation of Irving and Rossotti⁸. The proton-ligand stability constants of the Schiff-base ligands have been obtained using Bjerrum half-integral method. The same have also been calculated by pointwise calculation method⁹. The values agree closely.

The formation curves extend over a range of $0.160 < \bar{n}_A < 1.85$ for the ligand C_1 , $0.34 < \bar{n}_A < 1.924$ for the ligand C_2 and $0.126 < \bar{n}_A < 1.987$ for the ligand C_3 . The formation curve in all these cases have a wave like appearance. This indicates the formation of the species HL and H_2^+L (L=Schiff-base ligand), i. e., the protonated nitrogen and phenolic hydrogen undergo complete stepwise dissociation.

The formation curve in the case of Schiff-base ligand C_4 extends over a region of $0.178 < \bar{n}_A < 2.792$ and is also wave like, thus suggesting the stepwise formation of the species HL, H_2^+L and H_3^+L . In

the case of Schiff-base ligand C_5 , complete study could not be made due to the appearance of precipitate at high pH region. The available data would however permit the evaluation of only one, i.e., the $\log {}^pK_a^H$ value.

The value of the proton-ligand formation constants of the different Schiff-base ligands are summarised in Table 1.

Among the Schiff-base ligands C_1 and C_2 are monoprotic while the rest C_3 , C_4 and C_5 are biprotic in nature. In this connection, it may be mentioned that Kabadi *et al*⁹ have carried out a similar study on a compound C_2 under different experimental conditions and the relative magnitude of his values are nearly similar to those obtained by us. From Table 1 it is evident that the overall proton-ligand stability constant $\log \beta^H$ is in the order $C_4 > C_1 \sim C_3 > C_2$. It will be of interest to examine the stepwise proton-ligand stability constant values of the Schiff-base ligands in relation to their molecular structure.

In the case of ligands C_1 and C_2 the formation curves show two distinct regions $0 < \bar{n}_A < 1$ and $1 < \bar{n}_A < 2$. During stepwise dissociation the hydrogen attached to nitrogen will dissociate first¹⁰. We have therefore assigned $\log {}^pK_2^H$ as the proton-ligand formation constant corresponding to the proton affinity of nitrogen in the ligands. The formation curve of the compound C_4 exhibits three distinct portions $0 < \bar{n}_A < 1$, $1 < \bar{n}_A < 2$ and $2 < \bar{n}_A < 3$. Here $\log {}^pK_3^H$ value has been attributed to the proton affinity value of nitrogen.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE SCHIFF-BASE LIGANDS

Compound		$\log {}^pK_1^H$	$\log {}^pK_2^H$	$\log {}^pK_3^H$	$\log \beta^H$
Salicyl-2-amino-pyridine	C_1	9.15 ^a	5.90 ^a	—	15.02
		9.15 ^b	5.85 ^b	—	
Salicyl-anil	C_2	9.70 ^a	3.75 ^a	—	13.45
		9.70 ^b	3.75 ^b	—	
Salicyl-anthranil	C_3	9.25 ^a	5.75 ^a	—	15.00
		9.25 ^b	5.75 ^b	—	
Salicyl-m-amino-phenol	C_4	10.7 ^a	4.90 ^a	2.05 ^a	17.65
		10.7 ^b	4.65 ^b	2.05 ^b	
Salicyl-o-amino-phenol	C_5	—	6.0 ^a	—	—
		—	6.0 ^b	—	

a = Bjerrum half-integral value.

b = Pointwise calculation value.

In ligand C_1 , there are two nitrogen atoms : (i) the pyridine nitrogen and (ii) nitrogen belonging to the azomethine group. Of these the pyridine nitrogen may be expected to be more basic due to the inductive and mesomeric effects. This justifies the high proton-affinity value ($\log {}^pK_2^H$) of 5.85 of the pyridine-nitrogen in the ligand compared to a

corresponding value of 5.04 in the pyridine molecule. The reported value indicates further that the azomethine nitrogen virtually shows no proton absorption which is due to the close proximity of the electron withdrawing nitrogen of pyridine. The proton absorption constant for azomethine nitrogen of compound C_2 (3.75) is higher than that of compound C_4 (2.05), the higher value in the former may probably be due to the occurrence of more effective resonance between ketamine and the enolimine structure of the Schiff-base ligand¹¹.

An examination of the formation curve of compound C_3 suggests that the portions $0 < \bar{n}_A < 1$ and $1 < \bar{n}_A < 2$ may be independently considered in calculating the corresponding proton-ligand constants. The ligand titration curve indicates that dissociation occurs at meter readings below seven. Hence the determined $\log {}^pK_2^H$ value of 5.75 may be ascribed to the dissociation of the strongly acidic $-\text{COOH}$ group. The nitrogen atom, however, shows little proton absorption which may be due to the presence of electron withdrawing $-\text{COOH}$ group in a position ortho to it.

The $\log {}^pK_1^H$ value of ligands C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4 refer to the proton-ligand formation constant value corresponding to the dissociation of the phenolic hydrogen attached to the salicylaldehyde moiety. For C_5 the corresponding value could not be obtained due to appearance of precipitate. The stability constant values ($\log {}^pK_1^H$) of the ligands follow the following order

A high value obtained for the dissociation of phenolic $-\text{OH}$ in compound C_4 indicates the occurrence of effective intramolecular hydrogen bonding between the azomethine nitrogen and phenolic hydrogen (salicylic $-\text{OH}$). Relative lowering of the corresponding value in compound C_2 may be due to the presence of electron withdrawing inductive effect of the phenyl group attached to the azomethine nitrogen. In C_3 there is a possibility of additional hydrogen bonding as

Fig. 1

shown Fig. 1. Such an additional hydrogen bonding might lead to a lower $\log {}^pK_1^H$ value since the phenolic hydrogen would now be less strongly held by the azomethine nitrogen. In C_1 , the azomethine nitrogen can less effectively participate

in intramolecular hydrogen bonding due to the electron-withdrawing effect of pyridine-nitrogen and hence a lower $\log {}^pK_1^H$ value is expected.

$\log {}^pK_2^H$ value of compounds C_4 and C_5 correspond to the dissociation of phenolic hydrogen of the aminophenol moiety. In C_5 , there is a possibility of new intramolecular hydrogen bonding between the azomethine nitrogen and the aminophenolic $-\text{OH}$ in the ortho position, in addition to the one already existing between the same nitrogen and the salicylic $-\text{OH}$ (Fig. 2).

Fig 2

Such hydrogen bonding will lead to an increase in dissociation value ($\log {}^pK_2^H$) of the *o*-amino phenolic $-\text{OH}$ in C_5 compared to that of *m*-aminophenolic $-\text{OH}$ in C_4 where no such hydrogen bonding is possible.

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